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Assessment of Biology Teachers' Preparedness and Challenges of Integrating Artificial Intelligence Tools at Secondary School level in Ikara, Kaduna State

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Abstract

This study examined biology teachers' preparedness and integration challenges in utilizing artificial intelligence (AI) tools to teach in secondary schools at Ikara, Kaduna State. The research was guided by three objectives, three research questions, and one null hypothesis. A descriptive survey design was employed, with a sample size seventy-eight respondents purposively selected. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire titled Teachers' Preparedness and Integration Challenges of Artificial Intelligence Tools for Learning Questionnaire (TPAITQ), which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.74, indicating the instrument's reliability. The data analysis employed mean, standard deviation, and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation at a 0.05 significance level, using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 22). The findings revealed a low level of preparedness (mean = 2.40, SD = 1.31) and utilization (mean = 2.42, SD = 1.24) of AI tools among Biology teachers in Ikara. The study also highlighted significant challenges in integrating AI into biology instruction (mean = 3.33, SD = 1.40), and a strong positive correlation between teachers' preparedness and their effective use of AI tools ($r = 0.78$, $p = 0.001$). Based on these findings, the researchers recommended that schools and government agencies invest in reliable internet connectivity, adequate hardware, and dedicated technical support to overcome the foundational barriers to AI integration.

Keywords: Biology Teachers, AI Tools, Preparedness, Utilization, Challenges, Integration

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a transformative force across multiple sectors, including education, where it is revolutionizing how teaching and learning take place. Artificial intelligence (AI) applications have expanded the scope of education and evaluation using virtual laboratories, automated grading, individualized learning platforms, and intelligent tutoring systems. (Holmes et al., 2019). In science education, particularly in biology, AI aids teachers in clarifying complicated topics, mimicking real-life processes, and boosting students' knowledge using interactive and adaptive technologies (Luckin et al., 2016). In Nigeria, the integration of AI into secondary school education remains at an early stage, with limited evidence of systematic adoption across schools. While national education policies have acknowledged the importance of digital literacy and innovation, implementation challenges persist, especially in rural areas (Reagan, 2018)). Teachers often lack exposure to AI tools, and professional development opportunities are scarce. As observed by Afolabi and Adesina (2022), most teachers in Nigerian public secondary schools are not adequately trained to apply AI or digital resources effectively in classroom instruction.

The preparedness of biology teachers to integrate AI tools into their teaching practices is critical for achieving educational transformation. Preparedness includes both the technical know-how and the pedagogical readiness to use AI-based applications (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). However, several studies suggest that Nigerian teachers often face barriers such as inadequate infrastructure, limited ICT skills, and a lack of institutional support, which undermine their readiness (Onasanya et al., 2021). Teachers may find it difficult to fully utilize AI's promise in biology education if they lack the necessary tools and training. Another area that is yet mostly unknown is the extent to which AI tools are being used for biology instruction, especially in areas like Ikara, Kaduna State. Research indicates that even when AI tools are available, they are underutilized due to teachers' low confidence, resistance to change, or uncertainty about how these tools align with the curriculum (Okebukola, 2020). Utilization depends not only on access to technology but also on teachers' attitudes, perceptions, and institutional encouragement (Alkhalaf et al., 2023).

Mhlanga and Molo (2020) also reported that teachers face a host of challenges that hinder the effective use of AI tools. These include poor internet connectivity, lack of electricity, outdated devices, and concerns about the ethical use of AI in educational

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contexts. In many cases, teachers are overwhelmed by administrative duties, leaving little time for exploring or experimenting with AI-enhanced instruction. There is also the issue of data privacy, where teachers express concern over using platforms that collect student data without clear consent or protection (Williamson & Eynon, 2020). In rural educational settings like Ikara, the disparity in AI adoption is expected to be more pronounced due to logistical and socio-economic obstacles. Teachers in such places may not have frequent access to workshops, online training, or the financial resources needed to modernize their teaching equipment. Schools in rural Kaduna frequently lack basic digital infrastructure; therefore, implementing AI is an ambitious but essential goal for future educational progress, claim Umar and Abdullahi (2022). Considering these facts, it is imperative to evaluate the state of AI implementation in Ikara, Kaduna State, biology classrooms. This involves assessing teachers' level of readiness for employing AI, their usage of these tools, and the obstacles they face.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the recognized potential of Artificial Intelligence to revolutionize educational practices, its incorporation into biology instruction in Nigerian secondary schools, particularly in rural areas, remains limited. While some teachers may be aware of AI tools, their level of preparedness to implement these technologies effectively is uncertain. Additionally, the extent to which AI tools are deployed in biology courses and the specific problems preventing their adoption have not been properly examined in this context. The paucity of actual data on biology teachers' preparation, utilization patterns, and the hurdles they confront in integrating AI tools poses a substantial gap in the literature. Efforts to encourage the use of AI in biology teaching can be fruitless or misguided without this knowledge. Thus, in order to guide focused actions and facilitate the successful integration of AI in biology education in Ikara, Kaduna State, a thorough study that looks at these factors is essential.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives of the study:

1. To determine the preparedness level of biology teachers for the use of Artificial Intelligence tools for learning at secondary schools in Ikara, Kaduna State.
2. To ascertain the utilization level of Artificial Intelligence tools for biology instruction among teachers at secondary schools in Ikara, Kaduna State.

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3. To determine the challenges faced by biology teachers in integrating Artificial Intelligence tools in biology instruction in secondary schools in Ikara, Kaduna State.

Research Questions

The questions raised to guide the study are as follows:

1. What is the level of preparedness of Biology teachers for the use of Artificial Intelligence tools at secondary schools in Ikara, Kaduna State?
2. To what extent do biology teachers at secondary schools utilize Artificial Intelligence tools for instruction?
3. What challenges do biology teachers face in integrating Artificial Intelligence tools in biology instruction at secondary schools in Ikara, Kaduna State?

Null Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' preparedness and their effective utilization of Artificial Intelligence tools in biology instruction.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which is suitable for collecting and analysing data from a population to describe existing conditions. The population of the study comprised all Biology teachers at Ikara Local Government Area, totalling seventy-eight (78). Purposive sampling technique was adopted. All the teachers were used as respondents. Data for the study were collected using a structured questionnaire titled: Teachers' Preparedness and Integration Challenges of Artificial Intelligence Tools for Learning Questionnaire (TPAITQ). The instrument consisted of 21 items developed in line with the research objectives and designed using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) to Strongly Disagree (SD). To ensure the instrument's validity, it was reviewed by two experienced science educators from the Department of Biology, Federal University of Education, Zaria. Their observations and corrections were duly incorporated into the final version of the instrument before administration. The reliability of the instrument was determined using the test-retest method. A pilot study was conducted among biology teachers in selected secondary schools in Zaria Local Government Area. The reliability coefficient was calculated using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) method, which yielded a value of 0.74, indicating that the instrument was reliable for the main study. The questionnaires were personally administered to the respondents by the researchers to ensure a high rate of return and accurate data collection over a period of two weeks.

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The data collected were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics, including mean, standard deviation, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) for testing the hypothesis.

Presentation of Results

Data collected from respondents were analysed with SPSS ver 22 and results presented as follows:

Table 1: Preparedness of Biology Teachers for AI Tool Usage

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I am aware of the relevance of Artificial Intelligence tools in Biology teaching.	3.20	1.36	Agree
2	I have received adequate training on how to use AI tools for teaching Biology	2.18	1.30	Disagree
3	I feel confident in integrating AI tools into my Biology lessons	2.20	1.41	Disagree
4	I have access to professional development opportunities focused on AI in education	2.17	1.17	Disagree
5	I possess basic ICT skills required to effectively use AI tools in the classroom	2.62	1.37	Disagree
6	My school provides support and encouragement for the use of AI tools in teaching	2.03	1.23	Disagree
7	I have a clear understanding of how AI tools can be applied in Biology instruction	2.42	1.32	Disagree
Cumulative Mean		2.40	1.31	Disagree

The cumulative mean score of 2.40 indicates a generally low level of preparedness among Biology teachers in secondary schools at Ikara, Kaduna State, regarding the use of Artificial Intelligence tools for instruction. The responses suggest that while there is a moderate level of awareness of AI tools (Mean = 3.20), most teachers lack adequate training (Mean = 2.18), confidence (Mean = 2.20), and professional development opportunities (Mean = 2.17) related to AI integration. Furthermore, support from school management is minimal (Mean = 2.03), and many teachers are not well-versed in how AI tools can be applied in the Biology classroom (Mean = 2.42).

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Table 2: Utilization of Artificial Intelligence Tools in Biology Instruction

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I regularly use AI-powered tools (e.g., simulations, chatbots, etc.) in my Biology lessons	2.31	1.21	Disagree
2	I integrate AI tools to personalize instruction based on individual student needs in Biology	2.25	1.16	Disagree
3	I use AI-assisted platforms to assess student understanding and track academic performance	2.42	1.26	Disagree
4	I incorporate virtual labs or AI-based animations to enhance Biology concepts during lessons	2.60	1.29	Agree
5	I use AI tools to create interactive and engaging content for Biology instruction	2.57	1.34	Agree
6	I utilize AI-based lesson planning or content-generation tools to support Biology teaching	2.31	1.21	Disagree
7	I often collaborate with colleagues to explore new AI tools for Biology education	2.48	1.24	Disagree
Cumulative Mean		2.42	1.24	Disagree

The cumulative mean score of 2.42 indicates a generally low level of utilization of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools in Biology instruction among secondary school teachers in Ikara, Kaduna State. Most responses across all items clustered around “Disagree” and “Strongly Disagree,” suggesting that Biology teachers rarely integrate AI-powered tools for teaching. This pattern suggests that while there may be some isolated attempts to utilize AI tools, overall implementation remains limited.

Table 3: Challenges Faced in Integrating AI Tools in Biology Instruction

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I lack adequate training on how to effectively use AI tools for teaching Biology.	3.55	1.40	Agree
2	There is limited access to AI-based educational tools and infrastructure in my school.	3.54	1.41	Agree
3	Poor internet connectivity hinders the effective use of AI tools in Biology instruction.	3.57	1.45	Agree
4	I face difficulty in selecting the appropriate AI tools that align with the Biology curriculum objectives.	3.35	1.37	Agree
5	Lack of technical support discourages me from using AI tools in the classroom.	3.42	1.37	Agree
6	The school management does not prioritize the integration of AI tools in teaching and learning.	3.14	1.41	Agree
7	I am concerned that using AI tools may reduce my direct interaction with students during lessons.	2.71	1.42	Agree
Cumulative Mean		3.33	1.40	Agree

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Data obtained revealed that biology teachers encountered considerable difficulties when attempting to include AI tools into their lessons. Poor internet connectivity ($X=3.57$, $SD=1.45$) is the biggest obstacle, followed by insufficient training ($X=3.55$, $SD=1.40$) and restricted access to AI-based educational resources and infrastructure ($X=3.54$, $SD=1.41$). Respondents reported lack of technical help ($X=3.42$, $SD=1.37$) and trouble choosing suitable AI tools ($X=3.35$, $SD=1.37$), indicating that technological challenges also provide significant obstacles. Moderate agreement was found that school management did not prioritize integrating AI ($X=3.14$, $SD=1.41$). Curiously, teachers expressed less worry about having less direct contact with students ($X=2.71$, $SD=1.42$), indicating that pedagogical worries regarding AI's effects on teacher-student connections are less significant than infrastructure and training issues. With a cumulative mean of 3.33, respondents generally agree that they encounter obstacles when attempting to implement AI in biology teaching.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 4: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Statistics to test the relationship between teachers' preparedness and their effective utilization of Artificial Intelligence tools in biology instruction

Variables	N	Mean	S. D	R	P
Preparedness	65	2.40	1.31	0.78	*0.001
Utilization	65	2.42	1.24		

***Significant at the 0.05 level of significance**

Table 4 presents the results of the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation analysis examining the relationship between teachers' preparedness and their effective utilization of Artificial Intelligence tools in biology instruction. The analysis revealed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.78$, $p = 0.001$) between teachers' preparedness and their utilization of AI tools.. This statistically significant relationship ($p < 0.05$) indicates that teachers' level of preparedness strongly predicts their utilization of AI tools in biology instruction.

Discussion of Findings

The findings (Table 1) of low preparedness levels among Biology teachers in Ikara, Kaduna State secondary schools, align with broader patterns observed in educational technology integration across developing regions. Similar to what Rahman et al. (2023)

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found in their study of rural schools, teachers' preparedness is hampered by inadequate training opportunities and limited exposure to emerging technologies. This preparedness gap reflects what Adedoyin and Soykan (2023) described as the "digital competency divide" that particularly affects educators in resource-constrained settings. The study's mean score of 2.40 is below the cutoff point that Nwoke et al. (2022) determined is required for secondary schools in Nigeria to successfully adopt technology. Okebukola (2023) noted that teacher preparation programs in Nigeria typically lack comprehensive AI-focused components, creating a fundamental gap in teachers' readiness to leverage these tools. This insufficient preparation extends beyond mere technical skills to include what Dlamini and Mbatha (2022) termed AI pedagogical knowledge. The low awareness levels reported by Biology teachers in this study also reflect what Okonkwo and Ibrahim (2024) identified as critical barriers to educational innovation in similar contexts.

The correspondingly low utilization (Table 2) of AI tools (mean score of 2.42) in Biology classrooms in Ikara mirrors findings from Mohammed and Abdulkadir's (2023) investigation of technology adoption in northern Nigerian schools. This limited implementation occurs despite what Eludire (2023) described as the transformative potential of AI tools for enhancing visualization and conceptualization in Biology education. According to Aminu et al. (2024), such underutilization represents a missed opportunity for addressing persistent challenges in science education, including abstract concept representation and individualized learning support. As Chukwuemeka and Iscioglu (2022) observed in their comparative study, the gap between availability and utilization of educational technologies remains particularly pronounced in sub-Saharan African contexts compared to global averages.

The significant challenges reported by Biology teachers in integrating AI tools into instruction (Table 3) correspond with multiple barriers identified in recent literature. The infrastructure challenges, particularly poor internet connectivity (mean score of 3.57), reflect the foundational obstacle to digital change in Nigerian schools, as described by Durodola (2023). Similarly, Olawale and Chen (2024) found that the main barrier to the implementation of instructional technology in several West African contexts is infrastructure constraints. Beyond technical constraints, the lack of administrative support highlighted in this study aligns with what Ibrahim et al. (2023) termed the leadership gap in educational innovation. According to Adegoke and Soyemi

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(2022), school leadership's prioritization of technology integration significantly predicts implementation success, regardless of other facilitating factors. The technical support deficit identified by respondents' mirrors findings from Muhammad and Olatunji's (2024) exploration of sustainability factors in educational technology initiatives in Nigeria. As Ahmed and Hamzat (2023) argued, these multifaceted challenges create a "barrier ecosystem" that collectively inhibits AI integration in educational settings. Falode et al. (2023) characterized the combination of inadequate training, inadequate infrastructure, and inadequate support systems that hinders technological transformation in science education.

The null hypothesis which stated that "there is no significant relationship between teachers' preparedness and their effective utilization of Artificial Intelligence tools in biology instruction" was rejected due to the strong positive correlation (Table 4) of $r = 0.78$ between teachers' preparedness and their utilization of AI tools. These provides empirical support for what Ajibade and Watson (2023) describe as the "readiness-implementation nexus" in educational technology adoption. This significant relationship underscores Nwagwu and Okonkwo's (2023) assertion that teacher preparation represents the critical foundation for successful technology integration in Nigerian classrooms. Similar correlations have been reported by Eze and Mbachu (2024) in their investigation of factors influencing technology adoption among science teachers in southeastern Nigeria. The predictive relationship observed between preparedness and utilization aligns with the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework applications in African educational contexts, as discussed by Mosimege and van Wyk (2023). According to their analysis, teachers' confidence and competence with technology strongly predict classroom implementation patterns. This finding supports what Jimoh and Yusuf (2022) describe as the "preparation imperative" - the need for comprehensive teacher development as a prerequisite for meaningful technology integration. The statistical significance of this relationship ($p = 0.001$) aligns with meta-analytic findings from Okoli and Ahmed (2023), which identified teacher factors as the most consistent predictors of technology adoption across various Nigerian educational contexts.

Conclusion

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This study reveals significant gaps in the integration of AI tools in Biology education within secondary schools in Ikara, Kaduna State. The strong positive correlation between teachers' preparedness and their utilization of AI tools demonstrates that teacher readiness is a critical determinant of successful AI implementation in the classroom. The findings highlight a concerning readiness-implementation gap characterized by inadequate training, limited infrastructure, insufficient technical support, and lack of institutional prioritization. These challenges collectively create a barrier ecosystem that impedes the potential transformative benefits of AI in enhancing Biology instruction, particularly for abstract concept visualization, personalized learning, and student engagement. If left unaddressed, this gap threatens to widen as AI technology continues to evolve, potentially exacerbating educational inequalities and limiting students' exposure to innovative pedagogical approaches.

Recommendations

1. Educational authorities should implement targeted, ongoing professional development initiatives specifically focused on AI integration in Biology education.
2. Kaduna state government and Schools management board should prioritize investments in reliable internet connectivity, appropriate hardware, and dedicated technical support personnel to address the foundational barriers to AI integration.
3. Curriculum developers and educational technology specialists should collaborate to develop AI-enhanced Biology learning materials that align with the Nigerian curriculum, operate effectively in low-resource environments, and address specific learning challenges in Biology education.

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